

Milestone 26: Definition of Key Performance Indicators related to ACTRIS service provision

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1 Purpose

This reports proposes a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to allow the assessment of the provision of access to ACTRIS services in both quantitative and qualitative manner. While ACTRIS aims at offering high quality services to wide user communities, a monitoring system is essential to assess the performance of service provision and improve the access process in order to ensure efficiency and effectiveness towards the users. This milestone addresses and describes the KPIs that may be used as input for the Access Management Plan (AMP), to be established during the ACTRIS Implementation phase, in order to support the user strategy with optimal provision of access to an adequate portfolio of services needed and to guide the future access activities in the operational phase.

2 Methodology

2.1 What are Key Performance Indicators?

A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is a measure to evaluate the performance in a specific domain, and is generally linked to specific objectives. A monitoring system based on KPIs is particularly important for Research Infrastructures (RI) that are, for the most part, publicly-funded. KPIs help to assess the progress of a process towards the fulfilment of the intended results, and allow identifying critical issues for improving the process concerned. Therefore, KPIs must be well chosen as a function of what is considered relevant, and require the setting of targets as desired level of performance and tracking of the process against that target, using adequate tools. KPIs should be periodically revised and updated within ACTRIS. KPIs are a basis for decision making to achieve a strategic and operational goal. A quality monitoring system based on indicators should be in accordance with the RACER technique (*Impact Assessment Guidelines, European Commission, 2005*): Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy, Robust (see table 1 for more details). Furthermore, the choice of indicators should be aligned with the overall objectives of the RI and be based on SMART: Specific, Measureable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-bound (table 2).

Although different indicators may be applied to track performance, only the key performance indicators are relevant and critical to the success of the RI. KPIs are an important monitoring tool and must enable the following aspects:

- ✓ Monitoring of progress,
- ✓ Evidence-based decision-making,
- ✓ Development of future strategies,
- ✓ Contribution to successful communication of results and achievements,
- ✓ Increased transparency,
- ✓ Contribution to financial sustainability.

Table 1: RACER criteria for potential indicators to measure the achievement of an objective with respect to progress and results.

RACER criteria	
Relevant	Closely linked to the objectives
Acceptable	Acceptable for stakeholders and staff
Credible	Unambiguous and easy to understand
Easy	To monitor and at low possible costs
Robust	Against manipulation

Table 2: SMART criteria as a guide for setting of objectives

SMART Objectives	
Specific	Target a specific area for improvement
Measureable	Quantify to allow measuring progress
Attainable	Can be feasibly achieved, given the time and resources
Relevant	Aligned with the objectives
Time-bound	Related to a specific time period

2.2 How to measure performance of ACTRIS service provision?

Indicators are important for measuring the relevance of a given RI and are also used by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) as a tool to evaluate the projects on the ESFRI roadmap (*Indicators of pan-European relevance of Research Infrastructures, ESFRI Report, 2013*). **One of the high priorities of a given RI is the facilitation of access to resources and services and maximisation of their use.** ACTRIS will offer a wide portfolio of services, comprising both wide and competitive access, and will provide different kinds of access (virtual, physical, remote). In order to optimally implement the overall service provision, ACTRIS aims at putting into place a monitoring system based on indicators that will enable to evaluate its performance for service provision, improve and facilitate the access to its services, and adopt a suitable user strategy. Both the key players in the access process as well as the relevant criteria categories are presented below. The performance indicators are compliant with the ACTRIS data policy and ACTRIS access and service policy.

➤ Key players in the access process

ACTRIS is a science-driven and user-oriented research infrastructure that provides facilities, products, tools, and services for a wide range of user communities to support high-level research and facilitate international cooperation. Performance indicators related to ACTRIS service provision aim at assessing the quality and efficiency of the service provision in order to contribute to efficient management and monitoring of the overall access process, involving all key actors in the access process:

- **Users**, being the key beneficiary to advance scientific and technological knowledge, create new products and methodologies, and contribute to innovation. ACTRIS users originate from various communities worldwide. Although typical users are primarily researchers from atmospheric

sciences, ACTRIS attracts and serves users from environmental sciences and other neighbouring fields. ACTRIS benefits furthermore users from the public sector (climate and monitoring services, and official authorities) as well as the private sector for development of new technologies and products.

- **Access providers**, representing an ACTRIS Central Facility or a National Facility that has the capacity to make the ACTRIS services, tools, and products available to the users.
- **Service Access Management Unit**, being the functional unit within the ACTRIS Head Office representing the interface between the users and the services offered and responsible for establishing and managing the access process, interacting with the access providers, and coordinating the selection process with the review panel.

➤ **Considerations for defining access performance indicators**

Performance indicators related to ACTRIS service provision should be defined in order to allow i) the monitoring and assessment of the performance of the access provision to users and ii) the management of the overall access process against set targets. It will be ensured that the indicators are RACER and SMART and used in line with the below aspects:

Monitoring of progress	→	Based on quantitative information on the size and extent of the access provision, and user information
Evidence-based decision-making	→	Towards the achievement of the desired objectives for service provision and in line with the overall user strategy
Development of future strategies	→	As a function of evolving user needs and requirements
Contribution to successful communication of results and achievements	→	Periodic reporting of the results of the RI service provision and for dissemination purposes
Increased transparency	→	Realistic assessment of the success or the RI activities and towards users
Contribution to financial sustainability	→	Cost efficient services and access capabilities

Performance indicators can be both quantitative and qualitative, and can be categorized into different metric types (see also *Description of performance criteria for open access and list of performance indicators, ENVRIplus deliverable report 2018*):

- I. **Organisational metrics**, to evaluate the quality of organising and managing the access process and service provision, interactions between the key players, and of reporting and disseminating the results;
- II. **Operational metrics**, to evaluate the quantity of the services offered and access provided;
- III. **User metrics**, to evaluate the size and extent of the user community, the user interest and satisfaction;
- IV. **Strategic metrics**, to evaluate the progress as well as the relevance and impact of the service provision;
- V. **Financial metrics**, to evaluate the cost effectiveness of the service provision and relevance to the RI's financial sustainability.

Access-related indicators should allow to efficiently monitor the access and service provision, measure the progress, track the degree of performance change over time, evaluate if the ACTRIS services provision is successful and satisfying from the user point of view, and apply corrective actions when or wherever necessary. KPIs should therefore be revised on a regular basis and updated whenever necessary.

3 Performance Indicators for assessing ACTRIS service provision

The tables below propose a set of indicators related to ACTRIS services provision, sorted by metric type. Possible relevant KPIs from the suggested list are highlighted, although all indicators may be used for monitoring purposes. Target values are not indicated but must be specified when implementing the service provision, in accordance with the user strategy and the specific implementation plans for the Central Facilities. Each KPI will be applied over a specified time period by comparing obtained results against the target values, allowing calculating the achievement and inferring the overall performance. KPI target values may have to be revised and/or adjusted on a periodical basis.

3.1 Organisational metrics

The organisational metrics listed below aim at evaluating the quality of organising and managing the access process with respect to visibility and efficient interaction between the key players.

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
Visibility	ACTRIS service catalogue traffic (number of IP addressees accessing the ACTRIS web portal, number of page views, etc.)	quantitative	Measure of visibility and web presence
	Time spent in exploring the ACTRIS service catalogue	quantitative	Measure of relevance of service catalogue
	Number of ACTRIS Science and User Forum Followers/Members	quantitative	Measure of forum's visibility and attractiveness
	Number of visitors from social media	quantitative	Measure of visibility in social media
Access process	Number of user helpdesk requests	quantitative	Measure of capacity for stimulating user interest
	Number of comments in science and user forum	quantitative	Measure of capacity for stimulating user interaction
	Average duration of access process, in days (from date of user request to acceptance by SAMU)	quantitative	Measure of ACTRIS readiness for services provision to users
	Average duration of evaluation of user request by selection panel, in days	quantitative	Measure of readiness of review panel
	Level of access provider satisfaction of access process and interactions	Semi-quantitative	Measure of access providers satisfaction: not satisfied (1), slightly satisfied (2),

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
			moderately satisfied (3), very satisfied (4), extremely satisfied (5)
	Level of SAMU satisfaction of access process and interactions	Semi-quantitative	Measure of SAMU satisfaction: not satisfied (1), slightly satisfied (2), moderately satisfied (3), very satisfied (4), extremely satisfied (5)

3.2 Operational metrics

The following operational metrics aim at evaluating the capacity of the ACTRIS service provision.

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
RI capacity	Number of facilities (CF, NF) available for service provision to users	quantitative	Measure of operational capacity for service provision
	Percentage of NF/CF downtime not planned in advance	quantitative	Measure of operational reliability
	Number of services available to users	quantitative	Measure of RI service capacity
	Percentage of planned services not available to users	quantitative	Measure of operational reliability
Access statistics	Number of services requested by users	quantitative	Measure of user demand
	Number of requested services accepted by SAMU	quantitative	Measure of quality of user request
	Number of requested services provided to users	quantitative	Measure of operational capacity for access provision
	Number of data sets, data products, or digital tools provided to users via virtual access	quantitative	Measure of user demand on each data set (and variable), data product, or digital tool accessed through communication network
	Number of services by access type (physical, remote access) provided to users via SAMU	quantitative	Measure of user demand on specific service access via hands-on access, remotely, or through communication network
	Quantity of access provided to users in units of access	quantitative	Measure of the quantity of access provided, expressed in corresponding units of access of the service concerned access

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
	Quantity of virtual/ physical/ remote access provided in units of access	quantitative	Measure of operational capacity for access provision as a function of access type

3.3 User metrics

The user metrics aim at evaluating the size and extent of the user community, as well as the user need and satisfaction.

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
User access	Number of user requests for access received by SAMU	quantitative	Measure of the total number of requests received from users
	Number of users served	quantitative	Measure of the ACTRIS capacity to serve users
	Number of users per country	quantitative	Measure of the origin of users per country
	Number of services provided per country	quantitative	Measure of the use of the services per country
	Percentage of users originating in ACTRIS member or observer countries	quantitative	Measure of the user base within the RI perimeter
	Percentage of users originating in European countries	quantitative	Measure of the user base within Europe
	Percentage of users originating in countries outside Europe	quantitative	Measure of the user base worldwide and of the capacity for international collaboration
User type	Number of users per scientific field	quantitative	Measure of the capacity for attracting users from other domains
	Number of users from academic and public research organisations	quantitative	Measure of users from academic and public research organisations
	Number of users from public sector	quantitative	Measure of users from public sector
	Type of public sector users	qualitative	Measure of diversity of users from public sector
	Number of users from private sector (business and industry)	quantitative	Measure of users from private sector
	Type of private sector use	qualitative	Measure of diversity for using the services by the private sector

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
User profile	Percentage of new users	quantitative	Measure of attracting new users
	Percentage of recurrent users	quantitative	Measure of reliability of service provision
	Percentage of experienced users	quantitative	Measure of user experience level
	Percentage of young users (students, early career scientists, ...)	quantitative	Measure of training capacity
	Percentage of female users	quantitative	Measure of gender balance
User needs	Number and type of service requested by user	quantitative, qualitative	Measure of user needs (scientific exploration, technological needs, training, innovation, modelling etc.)
User feedback	Ease of finding information about ACTRIS services and access	qualitative	Level of visibility of information on access and services: very difficult (1), difficult (2), neutral (3), easy (4), very easy (5)
	Ease for contacting and interacting with SAMU	qualitative	Measure of user satisfaction for interacting on access-related issues: not satisfied (1), slightly satisfied (2), moderately satisfied (3), very satisfied (4), extremely satisfied (5)
	Ease of use of ACTRIS access interface	qualitative	Level of user friendliness of interface: very difficult (1), difficult (2), neutral (3), easy (4), very easy (5)
	Quality of access process	qualitative	Measure of user satisfaction of access process: not satisfied (1), slightly satisfied (2), moderately satisfied (3), very satisfied (4), extremely satisfied (5)
	Quantity of documentation on access and service	qualitative	Adequacy of available information: very poor (1), poor (2), average (3), good (2), excellent (5)
	Quality of documentation on access and service	qualitative	Quality of available information: very poor (1), poor (2), average (3), good (2), excellent (5)
	Quality of on-site support for accessing the services	qualitative	Quality and adequacy of available support: online support for virtual access, scientific/ technical/ administrative/ logistic support for physical and remote access: very poor (1), poor (2), average (3), good (2), excellent (5)
	Quality of service(s) provided	quantitative	Level of user satisfaction concerning services provided: not satisfied (1), slightly satisfied (2), moderately satisfied

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
			(3), very satisfied (4), extremely satisfied (5)

3.4 Strategic metrics

The strategic metrics measure whether the access provision achieves the expected effects in the short, intermediate, and long term, suggesting indicators for evaluating the relevance and impact of the service provision.

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
Impact on communication	Increase in number of communication activities	quantitative	Measure of dissemination capacity
	Number of citations of ACTRIS-related publications	quantitative	Measure of enlarged scientific audience
	Number of communications in media	quantitative	Measure of public visibility
Impact on outreach	Increase in number of user requests	quantitative	Measure of growth of user needs
	Increase in number of services provided	quantitative	Measure of growth of service capacity
	Increase in number of users served	quantitative	Measure of growth of user community
	Increase in number of users from different countries	quantitative	Measure of growth of user community
Impact on research	Increase in number of users in the atmospheric domain	quantitative	Measure of capacity to respond to user needs in ACTRIS scientific domain
	Increase in number of users from other than atmospheric domain	quantitative	Measure of cross-disciplinary capacity
	Increase in new services offered to users	quantitative	Measure of capacity to adapt to evolving user needs
	Number of citations of ACTRIS-related publications	quantitative	Measure of relevance of research output due to ACTRIS
	Number of peer-reviewed papers resulting from use to services	quantitative	Measure of production of knowledge due to ACTRIS services
Impact on technology	Increase of measurement quality	qualitative	Measure of capacity for improvement: very low (1), low (2), moderate (3), high (2), very high (5)
	Degree of technological development (instrument testing, development, new products)	semi-quantitative	Measure of capacity for technological development resulting from services: very low (1), low (2), moderate (3), high (2), very high (5)
Impact	Increase in number of young users and early career scientists	quantitative	Measure of training capacity

Category	Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
	Increase in number of new users from new regions/countries	quantitative	Measure of training capacity
Impact on innovation	Increase in number of users from private sector	quantitative	Measure of attractiveness towards the private sector
	Number of patents	quantitative	Measure of innovation capacity
	Number of technology transfer activities (public-private)	quantitative	Measure of innovation capacity

3.5 Financial metrics

The financial metrics aim at evaluating the cost effectiveness of the service provision and relevance to the RI's financial sustainability.

Performance Indicator (suggested KPIs are indicated in bold)	Value type	Definition
Cost of service/year per number of services provided	quantitative	Measure of a service's cost effectiveness
Percentage of free vs paid services	quantitative	Measure for providing free vs paid services
Type of services available free-of-charge	qualitative	Capacity of the RI for providing free services
Income from user fees	quantitative	Measure of the financial return from paid user access

4 Recommendations and next steps

This document summarizes a comprehensive set of possible KPIs related to ACTRIS service and access provision that is based on different metrics to consider organisational and operational aspects, user criteria, strategic and financial issues. The KPIs to be used should be adopted not only for gathering of relevant information for monitoring of the service provision, but to also allow thorough analysis and prioritisation of the ACTRIS access and services for future strategic planning, aiming at providing efficient and effective access for users to its services, resources, and tools. In order to align the service provision to the user needs, the KPIs should be regarded as recommended indicators towards RI performance but may evolve in the future. Therefore, they should be revised periodically and be updated whenever necessary and according to RI needs. The confirmed KPIs to be used will ultimately feed into the Access Management Plan that will be developed during the implementation phase as one essential tools for monitoring of the performance of the ACTRIS service provision capacity.

5 Reference documents

ACTRIS Access and Service Policy (D2.6)

ACTRIS Data Policy (D2.3)

ACTRIS PPP Grant Agreement (N° 739530)

Description of performance criteria for open access and list of performance indicators, ENVRIplus deliverable report 2018 (D10.3)

European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures: Principles and guidelines for access and related services. Publications Office of the European Union, 2015. ISBN: 978-92-79-45600-8, doi: 10.2777/524573, KI-04-15-085-EN-N.

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https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/FI13_46_14_ESFRI%20Indicators_report_4.pdf

Impact Assessment Guidelines, European Commission, 2005, SEC(2005)791/3,

https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/sfs/documents/documents/sec2005-791_en.pdf

6 Glossary

ACTRIS access provider – organization(s) in charge of an ACTRIS Central Facility or a National Facility that arranges for users to have access to its services.

ACTRIS Head Office (HO) - a Central Facility coordinating and representing ACTRIS, and holding the statutory seat.

ACTRIS member - a country in IAC that has signed a Letter of Intent or provided political support to the ACTRIS ESFRI proposal in 2015.

ACTRIS observer - a country in IAC without a vote.

ACTRIS variables - the atmospheric variables measured within ACTRIS.

Central Facility (CF) - a European level ACTRIS component that offers ACTRIS data or other ACTRIS services to users as well as operation support to ACTRIS National Facilities.

Interim ACTRIS Council (IAC) - a council of ministry- and funding organization representatives of ACTRIS members before establishment of ACTRIS as legal entity (during the ACTRIS Preparation and Transition Phase), superior decision-making body of ACTRIS.

National Facility (NF) - an observational or exploratory platform providing data and/or physical access to the platform within ACTRIS.

Physical access – hands-on access of users to the services of an ACTRIS Central Facility or National Facility.

Remote access - access to an ACTRIS Central Facility or National Facility without users physically visiting the facility.

Science and User Forum - an open platform for users to interact with ACTRIS and to be established during the implementation phase of ACTRIS.

Service and Access Management Unit (SAMU) - a part of ACTRIS Head Office facilitating the access to ACTRIS services.

User - a person, a team, or an institution making use of ACTRIS data or other ACTRIS services, including access to ACTRIS facilities.

Virtual access - free access provided through communication networks.

Further terms are explained in the ACTRIS glossary on www.actris.fr.